

Polarographic Study of the Reaction between Sodium Tungstate and Malonic Acid

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The application of the polarographic method to the study of the reaction between sodium tungstate and malonic acid has led to the establishment of the combining ratio of the reactants as 1 : 2. The formation constant of the resulting complex, as determined by the method of Kolthoff and Lingane, has been found to be 1.048×10^{-4} .

Malonic acid has been found to form compounds containing six-membered rings, but these compounds are not so stable as the five-membered rings formed by oxalate ions. Schramm¹ has studied the formation of malonato-tetramine cobalt compounds in some detail. Dutta and Bose² have investigated the stabilities of complexes of malonic acid with some trivalent metals. Many other examples of metal complexes of malonic acid are found in literature³⁻⁸. Uranyl malonate has also been reported⁹. Banerjee¹⁰ has made a study of the reaction of sodium tungstate with malonic acid employing the monovariation¹¹ and continuous variation method of Job¹². The properties investigated were *pH*, conductance and optical density. The present study is the extension of this earlier investigation.

The polarographic method for the determination of the combining ratios of metal and ligand and the formation constants of many complexes has been employed by many workers¹³⁻¹⁷.

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EXPERIMENTAL

Polarograms were obtained by using a Tinslay pen-recording polarograph. Measurement of pH was done with a Phillips pH meter using a combined glass-calomel electrode. Analar quality chemicals were used in preparing solutions of sodium tungstate (standard), malonic acid (standard), phosphoric acid ($\sim 0.1 M$), and potassium chloride ($\sim 2 M$). Freshly prepared gelatine solution was used as maximum suppressor. All operations were carried out at room temperature ($\sim 18.5^\circ$). Polarographic reduction of W(VI) takes place in phosphoric acid medium as is shown by Meites¹⁸.

For the purpose of obtaining polarograms, solutions were prepared by mixing known and constant volumes of sodium tungstate, phosphoric acid, potassium chloride and gelatine. The concentration of the ligand solution was the only variable quantity. From the polarograms were obtained the changes in half-wave potential with the changes in concentration of the ligand ($\Delta E_{\frac{1}{2}}$), which are tabulated in Tables I and II. By plotting $\Delta E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ against the logarithm of the changes in the corresponding ligand concentrations ($\Delta \log_{10} Cx$) straight lines were obtained. Stoichiometric ratio and the formation constant were calculated from the expressions (1) and (2) respectively.

$$\frac{\Delta E_{\frac{1}{2}}}{\Delta \log_{10} Cx} = -p \frac{0.0591}{n} \quad \dots (1)$$

$$(E_{\frac{1}{2}})_c - (E_{\frac{1}{2}})_s = \frac{0.0591}{n} \log Kc - p \frac{0.0591}{n} \log_{10} Cx \quad \dots (2)$$

where p is the combining ratio of metal and ligand; n is the number of electron transferred during the redox process which for $WO_3 - W_2O_5$ is two, $(E_{\frac{1}{2}})_c$ is half wave potential for the complex; and $(E_{\frac{1}{2}})_s$ is the half wave potential for the metal.

The values of ' p ' and Kc were found to be 1 : 2 and 1.048×10^{-4} .

Consideration of the above values together with the tendency of the malonate ion to form six membered rings leads to the following structure of the tungstato-malonate complex where two coordinate positions of WO_4^{--} ion have been occupied by the two ligand molecules. This structure is backed by the electrometric and spectrophotometric studies done by one of the authors¹⁰.

TABLE I
pH of the solutions—6.55

S.No.	Concentration of the ligand i.e., Malonic acid	Log of ligand concentration	Half wave potential ($E_{1/2}$) volts	Change in half wave potential ($E_{1/2}$) volts
1	0.000M	0.0000	-1.000	
2	0.005M	-2.3010	-0.985	-9.015
3	0.010M	-2.0000	-0.970	-0.03
4	0.015M	-1.8239	-0.960	-0.04
5	0.020M	-1.6980	-0.955	-0.045
6	0.025M	-1.6021	-0.950	-0.05
7	0.030M	-1.5229	-0.945	-0.055
8	0.035M	-1.4559	-0.940	-0.060

TABLE 2
pH of the solutions—6.50

S.No.	Concentration of the ligand i.e., Malonic acid	Log of ligand concentration	Half wave potential ($E_{1/2}$) volts	Change in half wave potential ($E_{1/2}$) volts
1	0.0000M	0.0000	-1.000	
2	0.0025M	-2.6021	-0.995	-0.010
3	0.0050M	-2.3010	-0.975	-0.025
4	0.0075M	-2.1249	-0.970	-0.030
5	0.0100M	-2.0000	-0.965	-0.035
6	0.0125M	-1.9031	-0.960	-0.040
7	0.0150M	-1.8239	-0.955	-0.045
8	0.0175M	-1.7570	-0.950	-0.050

Sensitivity = 5; Damping = 4; Drop time = 2.8 seconds per drop.

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